

DEGREE PROJECT

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DEGREE THESIS TASK SHEET**Student's name: Namazov Ibrahim****Registration number:****T008525/FI12904/G****Neptun code:****P51W5I****Course: Business Development****Title of the thesis:** PPP – participation of private sector in the realization of public goals**Tasks:**

1. Review the most important characteristics of public-private partnership, and the circumstances and reasons of the appearance of it based on literature sources!
2. Compare the characteristics of the most relevant forms of the public-private partnership!
3. Analyze the public-private partnership cases with suitable methods (e.g. case studies, statistical analysis, etc.) to characterize its financial role in the public finance!
4. Evaluate the results, draw conclusions, make proposals!

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I agree to consult this thesis in the fall semester of 2022/2023.

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STUDENT'S DECLARATION

I the undersigned student named Ibrahim (Neptun code:P51W5I) hereby declare that the degree project is the result of my own work; I referred to the special literature and the means used in an identifiable manner. The results included in the degree project completed are allowed to be used by the university and the institution announcing the task for their own purposes free of charge, subject to any restrictions on classification as confidential.

Budapest, 10 day 10 month 2022 year

student's signature

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Abstract

This goal is this paper to analyze how Public Private Partnerships (PPPs) are used in a selected countries. The research aims to examine the advantages and disadvantages of various partnerships. This paper uses secondary data to describe something. In a time when national and local governments are experiencing financial challenges, the research defines and discusses the significance of PPPs, with a special emphasis on selected EU countries and Azerbaijan.

When it comes to hiring private legal entities for traditional public service, the government makes decisions based on the period and creates new contract types based on those terms and conditions. As these contract types evolve and change over time, "public-private sector cooperation" emerges. There are disagreements in doctrine about the benefits and drawbacks of this new model, as well as how to define its legal framework. This research focuses on examining and analyzing these disagreements in order to contribute to finding a solution.

Keywords: PPP, Partnerships, PPP in Europe, Public-Private Partnerships;

Introduction

Public-private partnership model - It is a financing model based on the realization of some investments and services that are partially or completely under public obligation by sharing the project's costs, risks, and returns with the public, private sectors through a long-term contract.

In developed countries, the PPP model, which entails the transfer of business administration to private sector under state control, is particularly prevalent in the health sector. In the 1660s, building projects for roads in England were the first to use the public-private partnership model. The implementation of the public-private partnership model peaked in the 1860s, especially after the industrial revolution, with canal and railway projects, but many investors went bankrupt due to the European economic crisis. Following the United Kingdom, the United States and France adopted the public-private partnership model. The Suez Canal, which was also backed by Egypt's governor, Said Pasha, and completed in 1869, appears to be the result of a public-private partnership.

The UK took the first step in the public-private partnership (PPP) model with the "Private Finance Initiative (PFI-Private Finance Initiative)," which was established with the private sector's cooperation and formed the general framework of this model after the legal barriers to private sector participation in the public sphere were removed. Following England's successful implementation of the model, many other countries have begun to do so within their own borders. While there were around ten countries working on PPP practices in 1999, the number has increased significantly since then.

Why is a Public-Private Partnership Beneficial?

- Financial constraints and the need for additional resources
- Implementing projects in a faster/shorter time and with higher quality
- Spreading financing costs over time
- Construction and operating cost efficiency
- Applying private sector business experience to infrastructure and service provision in the public sector - Sharing risks

Collaboration between the public and private sectors is becoming increasingly popular around the world. It is simply an agreement in which private entrepreneurs assist in the supply of public infrastructure. This study looked at the coordinated approach of the public-private partnership (PPP) as a change in the process, highlighting basic characteristics, benefits, and basic components of PPPs, as well as their success path. It also clarified the structure, process, and

delivery method of joint-venture (JV) PPPs and contract PPPs, as well as identifying project classifications that can gain from using PPPs. It showed that, despite a lack of funding, central governments have been effective in financing new construction projects funded by the private sector engagement, allowing for innovation in developing infrastructure. Joint-ventures PPPs, which entail the formation of a firm in which the public actor serves as both a regulator as well as a stakeholder in the collaborative operating company, as well as the sharing of associated revenues, benefits/losses, and expenses, are defined as real PPPs notwithstanding their local value. Concession PPP, on the other hand, has national value and entails the transfer of risks to parties best suited to manage them, but the private player is solely responsible for project funding.

PPPs are a form of public-private partnership that strikes a balance between state ownership and privatization. PPPs, according to Awodele (2012), should be considered a viable option to privatization and socialisation since they allow for the alteration of the institutional context without the loss of municipal authority. It has long been recognized as a vital vehicle for delivering public infrastructure improvements and public service.

PPPs are a rapidly developing method of acquiring infrastructure assets and related services a fundamental shift in the state-industry relationship (Ahadzi & Bowles, 2004). However, PPPs are not a completely new idea in infrastructure development. The concession created in 1854 to build and run the Suez Canal was just the initial PPP in recent history (Levy, 1996). In perspective, popular pressure either for or against the Canal choice in the 1890s was non-existent (El-gohary et al., 2006). It is a method of procuring building infrastructure wherein private operators are directly involved in the delivery of public services (Mustafa, 1999), but also where project financing is primarily provided by the private sector, with the reasoning being to combine public and private sector assets in the pursuit of more quality service provision. The Great Britain (UK) has been identified as the most active economy in the region for this cooperation, which is popularly known as Private Finance Initiatives, according to Wang, Chan, and Cheung (2009) and Deloitte (2006), in order to facilitate the spread of this procurement method, the most advanced institutional, legislative, regulatory, and corporate frameworks have been built.

In the meantime, other advanced countries such as the Australia, United States, Singapore, Spain, China, Germany, Canada, South Korea, Japan, Ireland, , France, Iran, Hong Kong, and Brazil, as well as The World Bank, for example, is an international organization, the European Investment Bank, and the United Nations, have endorsed the PPP agreement.

However, in poor nations, the lack of efficient, transparent, and participative policies, methods, and institutions may be a significant barrier to effective adoption of collaborative engagement initiatives. Budget deficits, aging or failing infrastructure, rising demand for government services, the search for improved productivity and creativity inside the provision of public services through the use of private sector management and training, the desire to introduce contest, and a lack of domestic experience, particularly in developing economies, have all been identified as essential drivers of public-private collaboration in existing literature.

The Canadian Council provides a classic definition of this type of public-private collaboration as follows: 'A co-operative venture between both the public and private sectors, constructed on every partner's knowledge and experience, that best meets clearly delineated public needs through suitable allocation of resources, dangers, and rewards' (CCPPP, 2001). As a result, the current study intends to:

- Investigate the collaborative structure of the public-private partnership as a transformation process in order to highlight its major characteristics, advantages, important principles, and success route;
- Investigating the fundamental or distinguishing aspects of joint venture (JV) and concession PPPs in order to gain a better knowledge of their structure, culture, processes, and delivery systems;
- Identifying project types that would gain from a public-private partnership.

Literature review

1. Review the most important characteristics of public-private partnership, benefits, key principles.

This list created by Ohiani (2014) the following benefits of using PPPs to provide a service or facility for the general public:

- Reduced expenses: Help the government avoid upfront capital expenditures and cut administrative expenses.
- Promote economic growth and job creation in your neighborhood.
- Project delivery times and lifecycle costs are decreased.
- Address the public sector's budgetary deficits.
- Promotes innovation in infrastructure development.
- Better "Value for Money" due to increased productivity, expense, and dependable and creative service.

Figure 1: Essential Elements of Public Private Partnerships (PPPs)

On the one hand, it aids in the development of a nation's infrastructure. Contrarily, due to the following PPP limitations, it is constrained.

- **Requires Risk for Private Firms:** By transferring risk to private enterprises, the public-private partnership burdens them excessively in the case of failure.
- **Variable Profitability:** The complexity, level of competition, associated risk, kind, scale, and impact of the project all affect how profitable it will be.
- **Increased Government Expenses:** Because of the project's high degree of risk, the corporations sometimes ask for astronomical compensation, which raises the government's costs.
- **Might not be Cost Effective:** On occasion, the government might not have a complete knowledge of the project's costs. If a private company had access to all cost information, the public sector might be misled.
- **Reliance on the private sector.** The primary disadvantage of the PPP strategy is how much the government relies on the private sector to initiate and carry out projects.

Ohiani (2014) also noted the following underlying principles that support the PPP arrangement:

- **Get more For Your Money:** Ensure that project assessments take into account service quality and dangers in addition to cost.
- **Public Attention:** Infrastructure development initiatives need to involve sufficient and early participation of stakeholders, including end users.
- **Risk Identification:** Risks are given to the party that can manage them the best.
- **Openness:** World-class governance and significant governance standards to boost trust.
- **Rivalry:** By removing unnecessary entry barriers and fostering and enforcing appropriate competition, you may ensure that corporate activities are responsive to competition and appropriate economic pressures.
- **Ability to Deliver:** Guarantee that the authorities in control of privately held infrastructure have the tools necessary to manage the business processes involved and to work together with their workers in the private sector in a similar scenario.
- **Performance- or output-based specified criteria should be built on the idea of "verifiable service standards."**

A successful PPPs arrangement may be achieved through the legislative framework, policy, clearly defined goals and a roadmap, cogent making business, development of human resources infrastructure financing framework, policy structure, and capabilities.

2. PPPs structure and models

The contractual agreements between a variety of stakeholders, including the state, project sponsor, project manager, financiers, vendors, contractors, experts, third parties (such an escrow agency), and customers, can make up a typical PPP structure, which can be fairly complicated.

The PPP structure is simplified in the following figure. The type of Partnerships, however, determines the PPP's real structure.

Figure 2: Typical structure of a PPP project.

Various parties involved in a PPP project are represented by the "expert" box on the right, including engineers (designers), contractors (builders), operators, and insurers.

Similarly, the "financiers" box on the left includes a variety of parties funding a project, including equity and debt financiers. These parties may include domestic and international banking and financial institutions, development banks, and comparable other organizations.

The financial institution designated by the project business and the lenders to manage an account known as an escrow account is often represented by the box labeled "escrow agent." The escrow system is set up to keep money accruing to the project business, including project revenues. The escrow agent distributes the money in the account to different parties in line with

the terms of the contracts. Additionally, a deposit is held in trust in an escrow account until a set of predetermined requirements are satisfied.

They are examples of commonly used PPP models - Build-Operate-Transfer (BOT) , Design-Build-Operate (DBO), Lease-Develop-Operate (LDO), Build-Operate-Lease-Transfer (BOLT), Build-Own-Operate (BOO) Design-Build-Finance-Operate-Transfer (DBFOT), Operate-Maintain-Transfer (OMT), etc

- 1) BOT - When developing a standalone asset rather than an entire network, a build-operate-transfer (BOT) project is often brand-new or "greenfield" in nature (although refurbishment may be involved). In a BOT project, instead of charging tariffs to customers, the project business or operator often derives its profits from a fee payable to the utility or government. Many projects are referred to as concessions in common law nations, including toll road projects, which are brand-new and have many characteristics with BOTs.

This approach executes all plans, constructs the infrastructure, and transfers property to the public agency while also assisting in determining the source of funding. The BOT model has different type of advantages. So, the model is focusing on strengths of PPP, they provide an opportunity to expertise. The BOT model also has limitations. It can apply only big projects and it has more transaction costs.

- 2) DBO - The public sector manages and finances the building of new assets in a design-build-operate (DBO) project. To achieve certain agreed-upon results, the private sector creates, constructs, and manages the assets. As there are no finance paperwork and a turnkey contractor plus an operating contract, or a portion added to the contract agreement covering operations, are normally required for a DBO, the documentation is often simpler than that for a BOT or Concession. The Operator normally receives a lump amount for the design-build of the plant, payable in installments upon achievement of construction milestones, and then an operating fee for the operational duration, with no or little financial risk on the capital.

- 3) BOO - Similar to a process of privatization, private contractors in this approach are in charge of the facility's earnings and losses. As a advantages of BOO model, they help to develop of private agency and they promotes privatization process. The BOO model disadvantage is that, public sector assistance was lacking during the financial crisis.
- 4) BOLT - According to this approach, the government grants a private company a concession to develop a facility with the eventual ownership being transferred to the government. The BOLT model advantages are, they give full power over government and effective delivery of public services. The model's main limitation is that due of the ownership transference, the private sector has less motivation
- 5) LDO - In this system, a public owner leases space to a private business. The private corporation is in charge of operations and maintenance as directed. The main advantage is that, .creates a platform for the successful operation of the private sector. The main disadvantage is that, there was no private sector funding raised.
- 6) DBFOT - In this approach, the private agency assumes control of the project's management for the duration of the concession. The advantages of DBFOT model are that, opens up domestic markets to competition from abroad and new suggestions from outside the public sector. The limitations of DBFOT model are that, higher private capital costs and expensive purchasing procedure.

3.0 Effects of Public Private Partnership Practices and Miscellaneous Application in industrial areas.

3.1 Expected Advantages

Although there are numerous expected benefits from public-private partnerships, the following is a general framework. The most significant advantage of the public-private partnership model is that it allows the public sector to distribute risk by transferring some liabilities to the private sector based on the project.

The public sector can improve its own financial situation, restore bad settlements, make new investments, and increase competition in its own region through public-private partnership projects.

The private sector's contribution to the creation of public benefits, and thus economic development, is justified at the international level, and it is believed that the dynamism, effective resource use, and quick action capability of the private sector in public partnerships will be a remedy for the financing need and clumsiness of the public sector.

The public sector benefits from the private sector's innovative approaches to the design of project facilities or the delivery of services through PPP projects. At this point, the entrepreneurial spirit of the private sector is being applied to public services.

Furthermore, the benefits to the public side as a result of the implementation of the public-private partnership model are summarized as follows: "rapid implementation of innovations, use of private sector skills, development of projects at lower costs, budget certainty, payment dependence on the service provided, life-cycle cost risk being left to the private sector, risks to the private sector." Public-private sector cooperation transactions are not shown on the public balance sheet, better use of public assets, and responsibilities are shared in the most appropriate way.

The benefits to the private sector from the implementation of the public-private partnership are summarized as "ensuring the private sector's focus on the result, encouraging the development of special skills," and "receiving value for money, maintaining the service quality standard" for the service recipients.

3.2 Losses Expected and Potential Issues

First and foremost, it can be argued that the state will perform the national public service with unity in practice from its inception to its continuation, and that the service will be distributed equally in this regard. However, while it may be argued that a facility built with private sector participation does not impose a financial burden on the government at first, given the long duration of the contract, it is clear that the same amount, if not more, will be spent from the state budget overall. In any of the service areas, a different problem may arise, such as when implementing the public-private partnership model in the health public service. It is argued, for example, that if the Ministry of Health, which decides on the need for a hospital in the national health system, makes a decision based on the needs determination and assessment system rather than the requirements of the service, it may result in hospital closures due to financing issues in subsequent processes. In the field of health, this process will have irreversible consequences. It is argued that in practice, public-private cooperation projects may not necessitate as close cooperation as they do in theory. It is also stated that public-private partnership projects may be privatized in some cases, resulting in failures in this regard and a negative connotation. Furthermore, it is possible that the cost of resources will be higher as a result of the private sector borrowing, and the service quality will suffer as a result of the transfer of state-owned resources to the private sector. Final losses, private sector profits from public resources, disruptions in public services, worsening working conditions, decrease in service quality, long negotiations and expensive legal and consultancy services for both parties, and high profit despite the private sector's low risk can be categorized as a desire.

3.3 Potencial Risks of PPP

There are several potential risks connected to public-private partnerships, including:

1. Corruption and bribery that occur throughout the tender awarding process. When only politically minded builders are awarded contracts, this occurs. This prevents other private businesses from making infrastructure investments.
2. Permit and clearance regulations that provide obstacles. Before a sizable PPP infrastructure project can be started, several project compliances, permits, and licenses must be obtained. The project, however, does not appear feasible to the private organization since several environmental, labor, land acquisition, and other restrictions necessitate multiple applications and lack a single window clearance. The Government's multi-level corruption and red tape also make it difficult for the corporation to obtain these certifications and permissions.
3. PPP companies take advantage of any chance to renegotiate contracts by blaming factors like decreased revenue or rising expenses, which has been the standard in India. When private parties use justifications such having "miscalculated" the project's cost and income potential to put off the signing of the agreements and hence the project, it is not solely the government's problem.
4. The lack of capital for both government and commercial businesses. The PPP model is used by the government to get finance for infrastructure projects and the expertise of private companies. However, large infrastructure projects need huge capital investments, which deters private enterprises from taking on the majority of the project's financial risk, which may or may not result in income in the near future.
5. Public sector banks loans going bad: To entice private enterprises to participate in the PPP model, the government also contributes some funding to the project and takes out loans. Both the government and the commercial partners are unable to return their debts when the project does not generate money, which it frequently does not. These loans eventually turn into non-

performing assets for the public sector banks, who are frequently the source of such capital borrowings.

6. Market and Revenue Risks: Money risk is present when a project is unable to earn the revenue that it is expected to. Any of the following factors might put a PPP project at danger of losing money or facing market risks. Lack of revenue from fares or tolls The revenue risk may arise if adequate money from fares or taxes is not available. In this situation, the private sector may ask the public sector for financial compensation. Additionally, it may ask the public sector to raise the prices or tolls or to prolong the duration of the concessions. Inadequate revenue from other operations The private sector might ask the government to prolong the concession period if revenue risk is present owing to inadequate revenue from other operations. Not enough traffic A PPP project will receive government funding if there is enough traffic. The government will not compensate the project if the volume of traffic is not adequate.

7. Financial Risks: Funds will often be raised for initiatives that demand a lot of operating capital. At this point, there are two ways that financial risks are present. These dangers need to be carefully considered by all parties. Foreign Exchange Risk When a project involves foreign currency exchange or international funding, exchange rate concerns might arise. Many emerging nations experience fluctuating foreign exchange rates, therefore this risk should be taken into account. Rate of Interest Risk When a sizable sum of money is borrowed for the project at changeable interest rates, interest rate risk is present. The money should be borrowed with a set interest rate to lower this danger. Additionally, it's crucial to forecast a loan period that is longer than the projects duration since otherwise, the possibility of an increase in interest rates beyond the load period might result.

8. Force Majeure Risks: Most hazards associated with force majeure are unconnected to the project. None of the project's participants can control or stop them. Natural Force Majeure Events are to blame for the majority of force majeure hazards. Natural forces also include catastrophes like cyclones, earthquakes, and floods. Although these dangers cannot be completely eliminated, taking earlier safety procedures may benefit the project and reduce costs. Both sides are equally responsible for this cost rise.

4. Current PPP situation in European countries, Azerbaijan and analysis

4.1 PPPs in Netherlands

In the Netherlands, interest in PPP has been progressively growing since the end of the 1990s. The Dutch government and market players currently perceive PPP as being a mechanism that enables the government to carry out projects more quickly and effectively than through exclusively public endeavors.

The Dutch government has primarily concentrated on the lessons acquired in the UK PPP sector while creating its PPP policy. Based on these lessons learned, the Dutch government created a three-pronged plan to maximize PPP's advantages in the Dutch market.

Many industry analysts thought the Dutch PPP market was following the example of more developed PPP markets like the UK and Germany after the launch of a number of pilot projects towards the end of the previous decade.

The Dutch PPP market, despite the fact that originally many projects were thought to be appropriate for PPP, did not completely live up to its optimistic beginning. It currently seems that this has changed, since the Dutch government has recently designated an increasing number of projects as being appropriate for DBFM, including the EUR 1.4 billion Second Coentunnel and the EUR 0.5 billion A2 Maastricht highway. In addition, there is also evidence of a slow rise in the number of PPP projects.

Political support - PPP has been increasingly popular in the Netherlands throughout time, both in the public and private sectors. The operations of the Kenniscentrum, the knowledge center for PPP, which has been actively involved in supporting the dissemination of know-how and exchanging experiences with respect to PPP in the Dutch market, are largely responsible for this increasing support for PPP. After determining in 2006 that PPP was supported by the Dutch government as well as the several ministries involved, the Ministry of Finance made the decision to change the Kenniscentrum's function by incorporating it into the Ministry of Finance. The division currently serves as an information hub and counselor to government organizations and is known as PPS Asset Management. Additionally, it offers the private sector

general data. PPS Asset Management develops rules and norms, shares expertise, and encourages collaboration between the public and private sectors. This body no longer serves as a promotional entity as a result. As a result, there is now no meaningful promotional organization in the public sector.

On the other side, the private sector has created a number of PPP promotion platforms, including OPPS and PPS Netwerk Nederland. These online communities exchange best practices for PPP projects and offer networking and educational opportunities.

The following industries in the Netherlands have completed PPP projects:

Accommodation:

1. Kromhout Barracks - located in Utrecht The development of an institutional complex with 2,000 employees worth of offices, together with housing, recreational, and medical facilities, is part of this EUR 193 million PPP project
2. Tax Office of Groningen -The DBFMO office building in Groningen, the Netherlands, and the Dutch Ministry of Finance Building are both a part of the EUR 185 million project. The Ministry's buildings in The Hague, which total around 66,000m², will be completely renovated as part of the EUR 105 million project on a DBFMO framework

Bridges and Tunnels: Amsterdam's Second Coentunnel. In this EUR 1.4 billion project, new underwater tunnel will be built beside the A10 ring road around Amsterdam, while the original Coentunnel, which opened in 1966, will be renovated and maintained. Over the course of the 30-year contract, the concessionaire will be compensated via availability payments. Five years are projected to pass during construction.

Education: The Hague's Montaigne School. The Netherlands bought its first PPP education project with this one.

Prisons: Airport Detention Center in Rotterdam. The DBFMO of a detention facility at Rotterdam Airport is a component of this EUR 70 million project;

Rail: The Schiphol - Antwerp High-Speed Line is made up of the EUR 6.3 billion High Speed Line South, which runs from Amsterdam to the Belgian border, and the Belgian HSL 4. The Netherlands' biggest PPP project to attain financial closure to date is still this one.

Overview of legal system

The Netherlands is a country that practices civil law and has a civil code. The legal system in the Netherlands is solid. Legislative changes are typically prompted by changes to EU legislation or as a result of discussions and developments with the appropriate ministries and other governing authorities.

Specific PPP/Concession law

There is no explicit legislation governing PPP in the Netherlands. However, PPP projects are theoretically permitted under the existing legislation. Several rules and regulations on a federal, state, provincial, and local level may be applicable, depending on the sector concerned (such as infrastructure, construction, culture, education, health care, social infrastructure, defense, trash removal, or development). PPP projects are far more popular now than they were in the past due to increasing public understanding of their benefits. The contemporary political debate focuses more on energizing and facilitating than it does on addressing issues of permissibility.

Therefore, it is unlikely that a special Dutch PPP Act will be created in the foreseeable future.

Local funding market

Early April 2009, the Netherlands formally entered a recession. The PPP market is now being impacted by the economic downturn and liquidity issues. It is particularly challenging to attract senior debt, which makes it difficult to get the necessary capital for PPP projects. The issues are as follows, summarized:

- Banks become more and more picky about the projects they want (and can) fund when the financial markets become less liquid;
- Banks now prefer to fund projects through club transactions since they appear to be unable to independently assess the total financing risk;
- Margin gaps are growing. Banks no longer agree to charge 80bps, instead preferring to charge 250bps or even more. Depending on how the base rate develops, expanding margins can result in higher funding costs;
- The loan tenor is no longer lengthy enough to fund the duration of the project. Nowadays, loans are often made for eight to 10 years, as contrast to the once-common tenors of up to 25 years. Shorter tenors inherently necessitate refinancing during the loan's lifetime. Who bears the risk of the refinancing is a crucial topic that has to be addressed in this regard;
- Banks are now thinking about using market disruption clauses in their facility agreements to claim their actual costs of funds when faced with funding gaps below the applicable interbank market offer rate because the "market disruption risk" has materialized;
- Wrapped goods are no longer offered, and monolines are all but extinct. Therefore, parties must once more consider "classic" financing options.

Despite all of this, the Dutch government is nevertheless very motivated to carry out new PPP projects since they are seen as a remedy for the current financial crisis. Additionally, international financial organizations like the European Investment Bank and the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development might actively participate in financing infrastructure projects that are having trouble securing the required (committed) private sector funding in the

current market environment. Additionally, a one-time upfront payment from the Dutch government upon project completion is considered a potential fix for the current funding issues.

Security issues

The fact that the financing has "limited recourse" or "non-recourse" status is one of the main features of DBFMO and DBFM contracts. Therefore, the project's financiers won't be able to exercise their rights under the loan agreement against the project vehicle's owners (or will only be able to do so to a limited level). As a consequence, the lenders' decision to lend money is based on the anticipated (uninterrupted) cash flows from the project, not on the shareholders of the project vehicle's solvency. Dutch law authorizes lenders to take security to ensure repayment, which supports a standard limited recourse project finance structure.

A variety of collateral is frequently utilized in combination with one another. Real land, boats and aircraft, inventories and transportable goods, securities like shares, bank account receivables, important contracts, cash flow, and intellectual property rights like patents, trademarks, designs, and copyrights are all examples of collateral. However, due to the public use of such structures, it is sometimes impossible to create mortgages on government buildings in PPP transactions. A direct agreement between the financiers, the contracting authority, and the project vehicle is frequently included to the standard security package.

This prevents the public sector partner from terminating the PPP agreement before the funders have had a chance to intervene to correct a default and/or transfer the rights under the PPP agreement, or the shares in the project vehicle, to an appropriate replacement contractor.

Reaction of the government to the financial crisis

The Dutch Minister of Finance described the actions the Dutch Government would take to combat the impact of the financial crisis with regard to the DBFMO and DBFM projects in a letter to the Chair of the Dutch Parliament on July 2, 2009. In this letter, the Dutch government outlined three areas on which it will concentrate with regard to PPP projects.

- Decreasing the needed number of financiers. Each of the three chosen consortia must currently secure fully committed finance, per the Dutch government's requirements. Given that banks are now only willing to participate in loans for relatively small sums, such a condition may force each consortium to get committed funding from up to 20 commercial banks for a project worth EUR 500 million. The Minister of Finance is now considering holding debt fundraising contests, which would require just the victorious consortia to secure committed finance, in order to prevent this.
- Decreasing reliance on credit. This can be accomplished by the government making a one-time payment after the project is finished. However, it is crucial that such a payout not be excessively large since the absence of risk would make it harder for parties operating in the private sector to provide the needed additional value. Additionally, the EIB has showed interest in funding Dutch initiatives. The Ruding Committee has also recommended that the Dutch government investigate the possibilities of institutional investors participating in the financing of the DBFMO and DBFM projects.
- Agreements should be adjusted to reflect recent market changes. For a period of up to 12 months, consortia might no longer be required to submit binding proposals in order to accomplish this. The Dutch government has determined that such lengthy durations are no longer feasible due to the high interest rate volatility and must be adjusted to reflect the present market conditions.

The Crisis and Recovery Act, which went into effect on January 1, 2010, and will remain in effect through January 1, 2014, was also released by the Dutch government. The Crisis and Recovery Act will allow for quicker and more effective processes for several project types, which will lead to the advancement of many projects in an effort to boost the economy and jobs. The Act primarily focuses on infrastructural improvements and encouraging the use of renewable energy sources.

One of the first nations in Europe to investigate the advantages of PPP was the Netherlands. The Dutch PPP market did not, however, completely live up to expectations despite a promising

start. However, in recent years, the Dutch PPP market has been steadily expanding as a result of both the financial crisis, which forced the Dutch government to expedite the procurement of many projects that are now thought to be suitable for PPPs, and the general understanding that privately funded projects are advantageous to both public and private market parties. As a result, market watchers believe that the future development of the Dutch economy depends on the success of the projects that are presently being procured in the Netherlands PPP market

4.2 PPPs in Poland

Poland's economy is still expanding, but due to the worldwide economic slump, that growth has slowed considerably. The Central Statistical Office reports that Poland's economy expanded by 1.8% in 2009. According to an OECD estimate, Poland is expected to see 3.1% economic growth in 2010. When Poland will join the Eurozone is still up in the air, though. At the earliest, it is unlikely to happen until 2015.

Poland is one of the PPP markets in Central and Eastern Europe with the highest level of development. Poland has cancelled a number of PPP projects under different restrictions, mostly in the road sector, even though no PPP contracts were terminated under the Old PPP Act. These including:

- the A1 Motorway – Rusocin to Nowe Marzy section (EUR 660 million) and Stryków to Katowice section (EUR 200 million)
- the Stryków to Konotopa section of the A2 Motorway (EUR 1,000 million)
- National Highways no. 62 (EUR 220 million) and no. 19 (EUR 220 million)

In Poland, public sector partners for PPP projects have included the Ministry of Infrastructure (for rail projects), the General Directorate for National Roads and Motorways (for roads projects), the Ministry of Health (for hospital projects), as well as local municipalities for other local PPP projects. PPP projects have also received strong support from the government.

Future PPP initiatives will profit from improved governmental coordination and assistance. According to the New Polish PPP Act, the Minister of Economy is responsible for popularizing and promoting PPPs, monitoring and reporting on the success of completed PPP projects as well as the viability of upcoming PPPs, including the prospects and terms of financial commitment from the private sector. Additionally, there are some interesting non-governmental initiatives to support PPP ventures, such the launch of the PPP Center in July 2008. In order to promote and track the progress of PPP projects in Poland, the PPP Centre, which is made up of a number of top international and Polish consultant companies, law firms, banks, agencies, associations, and commercial entities, was established. The PPP Center works closely with the Ministry of Economy and regional governments. It plans to generate draft paperwork to standardize forms of PPP agreements and procurement procedures and organizes conferences to address questions about the New Polish PPP Act.

Poland was ranked 71st overall and 33rd in the European zone in the 2010 Heritage Foundation and Wall Street Journal Economic Freedom rating. Overall, it performs better than the global average, and its ratings in the areas of freedom from corruption and investment restrictions are higher than normal. The local government has already announced the purchase of a few new projects intended to be conducted under the New Polish PPP Act or the Concession Act. The concessionaire is being chosen for several projects (like those in Poznan, Wrocław, or Kraków) including the building and management of parking lots. Projects in Warsaw, Katowice, and Bielsko-Biala, for example, are still in the planning phases.

Overview of legal system

Poland is a country that practices civil law and has a civil code.

Poland's judicial system is generally reliable. Legislative changes are often prompted by changes to EU legislation or as a result of consultation and development by the appropriate Ministries and other permitted organizations.

Specific PPP/Concession law

The Public Private Partnership Act of July 28, 2005 (the "Old PPP Act") was repealed by the New Polish PPP Act, which went into force on February 27, 2009. The Old PPP Act had received harsh criticism for being unnecessarily convoluted and adding an excessive amount of "red tape" to the process of implementing PPPs. In the past, the market overcome these issues by obtaining PPPs through different procurement techniques, notably in the roads sector, where PPPs were organized on a DBFO basis and obtained via the Act on Toll Motorways and National Road Fund.

The New Polish PPP Act was created to create a legal foundation for Poland's quickly growing PPP industry and is expected to enhance the PPP procedure. For instance, the Old PPP Act greatly raised project prices since it required a thorough and pricey analysis, which the New Polish PPP Act does not. The New PPP Act outlines the primary evaluation standards that the public and private partners must adhere to while implementing a PPP to determine whether the services are cost-effective. A PPP agreement must address a small list of crucial problems in order for the major risks to be fairly distributed among the partners. Which organizations can participate in a PPP is outlined in the New Polish PPP Act. The private partner might be a Polish or international company. Generally speaking, the public partner may be a unit of the public finance sector, an affiliate of that unit, or a specifically constituted corporation that is owned or managed by that unit of the public finance sector or that associate.

According to the New Polish PPP Act, the public partner's primary duty under the PPP Agreement is to collaborate with the private partner to carry out the project, including providing its own contribution. The private partner is required to implement the project for fair compensation and to bear all or a portion of the project's expenditures (unless incurred by a third party)

The relevant public and private partners may also agree in the PPP agreement to jointly establish one of the four legal entities listed in the New Polish PPP Act: a limited partnership (spółka komandytowa), a limited joint-stock partnership (spółka komandytowo-akcyjna), a

limited liability company (spółka z ograniczon odpowiedzialności), or a jointstock company. Such a company's goals and operations are limited by the parameters outlined in the PPP agreement.

Local funding market

Due to the economic downturn, which is impacting several CEE nations, including Poland, it is now difficult to finance major transactions, especially throughout the course of a project. With medium-term debt that needs refinancing, sponsors and funders are seeking for mini-term alternatives. Prior to recently, contracts required that payments be made in Zloty with the corresponding amount stated in Euros. However, it is now feasible to make payments in euros as a result of recent legislative changes.

The Polish government is still very motivated to carry out new PPP projects in Poland, since these investments are hailed as a remedy for the current financial crisis. The General Directorate for National Roads and Motorways, one of the largest investors in the Polish market today, with a budget of around PLN 23 billion for road projects in 2009.

Additionally, international financial institutions like the EIB and EBRD have been active in financing infrastructure projects (such highway projects) that have had difficulty obtaining private financing in the present market environment. Additionally, the government views the division of larger projects into a series of lower value/phased initiatives as a strategy to increase competitiveness and facilitate funding for infrastructure.

Security issues

Generally speaking, funders are allowed under Polish law to accept a security package that supports a standard limited recourse project finance structure. Funders have the right to demand security over any real estate involved in the project, important contracts, shares, and cashflows. It is significant to note that Polish law does not prohibit the funders, the project vehicle, or the public sector partner from entering into a direct agreement that limits the public sector partner's ability to terminate the PPP agreement before giving the funders the option to intervene to

correct a default and/or to transfer the PPP agreement or the shares in the project vehicle to a third party.

Receivables from the backers of a PPP project can be secured in Poland in a number of methods. The specifics of the PPP project and the needs of the funders will determine the type of security that is implemented. Here are a few illustrations of funder protection. Receivables may be secured by placing a "mortgage" in the funders' favor on real estate. The Act on the Land and Mortgage Register and Mortgages of July 6, 1982 will govern this type of mortgage. The special purpose vehicle created to carry out the project may receive contributions from both public and private partners in accordance with the New Polish PPP Act.

When real estate is donated, the funders may take up a mortgage on it. Depending on the court, the registration of the mortgage often takes two weeks to two months. A "registered pledge" is the second type of security that may be used, and it is governed by Polish contract law and the Act on Registered Pledges and the Pledge Register of December 6, 1996. To safeguard the receivables of State legal persons, local and international banks, and corporate organizations, a registered pledge may be formed. They are able to be established over movables or transient property rights, particularly receivables or shares. A written agreement and registration of the pledge in the pledge register are necessary to establish a registered pledge. The registration procedure ought to take around a week in general.

Establishing a "financial commitment" is another method of protecting donors' receivables. Financial commitments might be made that would give the donors priority over money that was deposited into the bank accounts of the project vehicle. In PPP projects in Poland, this method of protecting funders' receivables is widely employed, and it merely calls for the execution of the pertinent agreement between the project vehicle and the funders. There is no need to register.

Reaction of the government to the financial crisis

The Polish government presented the "Stability and Development Plan" on November 30, 2008, as a response to the global economic crisis and in response to the European Commission's recommendation included in the "European Economic Recovery Plan" (EERP) of November 26, 2008, in order to lessen the effects of Poland's weak economic situation brought on by the global economic crisis. This plan is currently being implemented and will continue to be so in the future.

This plan assumes that necessary actions will be taken, such as:

- financial sector stabilization (e.g., through guarantees and security provided by the State Treasury)
- demand stimulation (particularly investment demand stimulation) by making the best use of EU funds granted to Poland for the years 2007–2013
- consumer demand stimulation through lower taxes and labor market protection.

In the future, the Polish government plans to reform public finance, privatize a number of state firms, and sell other assets held by the State Treasury in order to reduce the budget deficit and development of the public debt and prevent a worsening of the economic situation in Poland. The process of privatizing businesses like Polish Shipyards (Polskie Stocznie) and energy utility Enea S.A. has already begun.

The Old PPP Act included several restrictions. As a result, no PPP projects were carried out under the Old PPP Act's guidelines. Alternative means of procurement were employed instead. It is anticipated that the New Polish PPP Act and the Concession Act would streamline the PPP process, enabling more PPP projects to reach financial closure more rapidly and stimulating Polish economic growth. However, the new PPP regulations won't be evaluated until they're used in some pilot projects.

There has been a substantial shift in the environment for PPP investments in the Polish market, and it appears that the Polish government has the political will to carry out new projects using the PPP formula. All PPP ventures have strong backing from the Ministry of Economy. In order to make it easier for foreign investors to participate in the Polish PPP market, the Polish

government has also undertaken various legislative steps to streamline the business-startup process.

4.3 PPPs in Hungary

Although huge State and budget deficits have been an issue in recent years, Hungary has created a reasonably strong and well-functioning market economy over the previous few decades. The worldwide economic crisis has made these issues much worse. However, given that PPP projects often do not appear on the State's balance sheet, these conditions could provide them an added boost. PPPs have gained popularity in Hungary recently, especially in the following industries:

- Education-related projects include schools and dormitories;
- Sports and leisure initiatives include the Budapest Sports Hall and other venues outside of Budapest;
- Prisons-related initiatives include prison projects in Szombathely and Tiszalök;
- Transportation-related initiatives include road infrastructure, including the M5 and M6 motorways (EUR 193 million) and rail projects;
- Urban regeneration; and
- Cultural-related initiatives include museums and theaters, such as the Palatinus; (EUR 212 million).

To manage the PPP initiatives run by several ministries, the Hungarian government established the "PPP Organization," an internal committee. Government Resolution No. 2028/2007 (II 28) outlines the PPP Committee's responsibilities and duties with regard to proposed PPP projects. The PPP Committee drafts enabling legislation, reviews and comments on proposed PPP

projects, keeps track of their development throughout the course of their existence, and assesses them after completion.

The Administrative Secretary of State for the Ministry of Economy and Transport serves as the chair of the PPP Committee, which is made up of representatives from:

- the Ministry of Economy and Transport;
- the Ministry of Finance;
- the Ministry of Justice and Law Enforcement;
- the Prime Minister's Office;
- the Central Statistical Office;
- the National Development Agency

PPP units are also present inside various ministries, such as the National Sports Office, the Ministry of Economy and Transport (which has a PPP working group), and the Ministry of Economy and Transport (which has a department dedicated to property management) (which has a PPP project office). This demonstrates that the administration understands how crucial it is for Hungary to keep using PPPs. Hungary was ranked 51st overall and 24th in the European zone in the 2010 Economic Freedom Index, which was issued by the Heritage Foundation and the Wall Street Journal¹. Even while corruption is still thought to exist, overall it does far better than the global average and excels in the freedoms of business, commerce, and investment.

Overview of legal system

Hungary is a country that practices civil law and has a civil code. The revised Civil Code was just approved by Parliament and will take effect in 2010. Before Hungary joined the EU, it was necessary to harmonise the law with the then-current EC principles. Since then, legislation has grown and evolved to guarantee conformity with the ever-evolving EU standards. Hungary has been having discussions about reorganizing the State budget for some time, and any actions

taken in that direction will have an influence on the legal system, particularly on the tax and public finance laws.

Specific PPP/Concession Law

There is no explicit PPP law in Hungary. Although law in Hungary has been changed to make it easier to implement PPPs and PPP activity has taken place in various areas, the word "PPP" still refers to a business idea rather than a specific legal phrase. A significant piece of law, Act 38 of 1992 (also known as the "Public Finance Act"), as well as many executive orders, have been modified to promote PPPs. The revisions provide a process for public sector companies to take on these commitments and helpfully consider PPP projects as "long-term financial obligations." Any additional long-term debt, however, may only be assumed with the public approval of the government or parliament. The guidelines for the approval process and the different pieces of information that must be presented to the appropriate decision-making authority are laid out in government decrees. PPPs are governed by both generic PPP legislation and rules that are particular to particular PPP projects in Hungary. The Public Procurement Act and the Public Finance Act are part of the general law, while separate legislation has been passed for the Budapest Sports Hall and the road projects. Act 129 of 2003, often known as the "Public Procurement Act," is a critical piece of enabling legislation that lays out the complete bidding process that PPP projects must follow.

A private sector investor is required to appoint a contractor to carry out the activity within 90 days of the concession agreement's execution. The contractor has to be listed in the corporate registry of Hungary. According to the Concessions Act, the concessionaire may get a concession in exchange for paying a concession fee to the procurement authority. On how the concessionaire will be compensated for fulfilling its responsibilities under the concession, however, there is no advice. Act 65 of 1990, often known as the "Act on Local Governments," is important to PPPs that are implemented locally. The Act on Local Governments forbids municipalities from taking on any long-term financial commitments in any financial year that exceed 70% of their expected income and mandates that they maintain a specific ratio between

their revenue and long-term financial obligations (less the value of the payment obligations becoming due in the given year). Local government is not covered by the Public Finance Act; instead, the Public Procurement Act covers all public enterprises owned by the central government. There hasn't been a formal standardization of PPP contract or tender documents as of yet.

Local funding market

Hungary has historically come under fire for its accounting procedures that enable PPP projects to be treated "off balance sheet"². The Hungarian State Audit Office has also criticized PPP initiatives on the grounds that the planning for such projects is inadequate since it does not disclose all the expenses of a potential PPP project, and that these hidden costs may jeopardize the stability of the State budget. The Hungarian State Audit Office is a politically unbiased impartial organization created by the constitution to oversee the financial affairs of the Hungarian State. The parliament of Hungary receives its reports.

In order to convince Eurostat that the Maastricht restrictions are followed and that enough preparation work has been done for possible PPP projects to ensure they get value for money, strong criteria must be utilized.

If local government and other independent local institutions in Hungary feel they will have enough money to cover their regular expenses, they may start local PPP initiatives. However, the previous permission of the Hungarian government and the PPP Committee are necessary for the following PPP project types:

- certain projects supported by the central government, such student housing or sports facilities;
- colleges;
- universities;
- local PPPs that need financial support from sources other than the local government.

Depending on the project's value, either the Hungarian government or the Hungarian Parliament may need to approve it (for projects worth more than HUF 500 million or HUF 50 billion, respectively).

On freeway construction projects in Hungary, accounting for property can be challenging. The government is the rightful owner of both the construction sites used to build motorways and the finished roads themselves.

Therefore, the decision of whether to record the asset created during the PPP project in the contractor's books, where it would thereafter be subject to contractor depreciation, or whether to record it in the government property register arises in accounting.

The accounting treatment of the PPP project is important for the public sector since one goal of PPP projects is to classify the assets as non-governmental assets so that the government may record them off-balance sheet. The PPP agreement resembles a long-term "built to suit" lease when it comes to "availability" PPP projects used to construct universities and public cultural organizations. These project agreements may be viewed as finance leasing since the government often intends to take ownership of the assets upon termination of the lease, which has two significant tax and accounting drawbacks.

The assets must first be documented and depreciated in the government's accounts, and secondly, the VAT liability computed for the whole length of the lease must be discharged at the beginning of the term. Therefore, it is impossible to achieve the goal of the non-governmental classification of the assets engaged in a PPP project (i.e. these will not be deemed as being off-balance sheet projects). In certain instances, the government has resolved this problem by acquiring the contractor rather than the asset held by the contractor, although this is no longer allowed. Sadly, there isn't a simple answer to this issue.

Commercial banks frequently participate in the financing of significant PPP projects since Hungarian projects are typically viewed as bankable ventures. Long-term capital at reasonable costs has become more difficult to get in the present market climate, and the market appears to be looking into the potential of obtaining financing from multilaterals in addition to commercial banks. In contrast to other structures, such as real estate financing, the market appears to view

PPPs and project finance in general as a workable and comparatively safe option over the long term, and it is anticipated that these projects will receive financing once the global economy starts to recover from the downturn.

Security issues

PPP project financing arrangements are fairly comparable to previous, non-PPP models. A complete security package, encompassing security over assets (real estate and immovables), income, bank accounts, and equity, is often implemented by financiers. Direct contracts with step-in rights are also commonly used. The assets that can be used for security purposes may be scarce due to the nature of the assets in some PPP projects. Real estate, which is owned exclusively by the State, is one example of this. Additionally, contractors are prohibited from being sold to third parties under the Public Procurement Act (as amended on 1 April 2009), which means that the original founders must continue to be members of the contractor until the project is completed.

The term "security trustee" is not recognized by Hungarian law; however, the Hungarian financing market has come up with solutions, and the frequently employed "joint and several beneficiary," "security agency," and "parallel debt" structures give banks the same level of comfort as they would typically receive in the case of a trustee. The majority of collateral (mortgages over real estate, fixed charges, floating charges, etc.) is recorded in public registers; however, some collateral (such as claim pledges, bank account pledges, and security deposits) is exempt from registration requirements. Such registrations are either very quick (same-day in the case of notarial registries) or, in the event that registrations take longer, there may be a side note assuring priority for the secured party.

While step-in rights for funders are acknowledged by Hungarian law, step-in agreements must be implemented through a complex contractual mechanism. The Public Procurement Act may prevent the financing party from: (i) performing the services itself; or (ii) if not performing the

services itself, passing the assets obtained by perfecting the securities to another company that can perform the public services in question. This risk exists when step-in rights are exercised. The legislation in Hungary is still ambiguous on this matter, and the courts have not yet considered it.

Reaction of government to the financial crisis

The Hungarian government has not taken any explicit actions to aid in the completion of projects amid the present financial crisis. As a result, since the economic slump, no projects have been started in Hungary. The M6 phase III Junction Dunaujvaros (M8) - Szekszard (M9) was the final project in Hungary to reach financial close 67 in July 2008.

The PPP Committee in Hungary is tasked with managing PPP initiatives run by several ministries. Additionally, PPP entities exist inside a number of ministries. This shows that the PPP implementation is being taken seriously by the Hungarian government and that PPP use will continue in Hungary. However, there are certain legal concerns and barriers that prevent PPPs from being implemented in Hungary. These are listed below:

- property ownership - specifically with regard to highways, problems over whether to record the asset's ownership in the contractor's accounts or the government property register emerge;
- accounting: Since one goal of the public sector is to keep assets off the balance sheets of public organizations through the use of PPP arrangements, ownership of property also has an impact on accounting and government budgets;
- public sector budgets - as was already indicated, public sector budgets may be impacted by the accounting approach of PPPs. By demanding prior clearance from either the central government or the Hungarian parliament, depending on the scale of the project, Hungary has attempted to limit the impact that PPPs have on public sector finances.

4.4 PPS in Slovakia

Despite being impacted by the current financial crisis, Slovakia's economy is nonetheless holding well. In the years to come, a comparatively substantial increase is anticipated after a decrease of almost 6% in 2009. The relative strength of the Slovak economy is demonstrated by the fact that, on January 1, 2009, it became the second of the accession nations to join the Euro. Despite the fact that information on PPP projects in Slovakia has been widely covered in the media over the last year, Slovakia does not have a sizable number of completed transactions. However, there are a lot of projects in the works, and the PPP way of acquiring transportation and social infrastructure is gaining popularity. Transport-related projects are leading Slovakia's transition to embracing PPP as a procurement strategy. The first agreement to achieve contract close in January 2009 was a PPP to implement electronic toll collecting equipment for heavy goods vehicles.

The first road infrastructure contract to conclude in Slovakia was the R1 Nitra - Tekovské Nemce, Banská Bystrica, northern bypass project, with a capital value exceeding EUR 1 billion. When the project reached financial close in August 2009, Project Finance International named it the 2009 Infrastructure Deal of the Year.

Separately, the Ministry of Telecommunications and Transport is at present contracting with PPPs for two significant road projects:

- D1 – Dubná Skala – Ivachnová, Jánovce – Jablonov, Fričovce - Svinia, having a capitalization of more than \$2 billion. This project was completed commercially in April 2010, and financial closing is anticipated for the summer of 2010.
- D1, Phase 3 – Hričovské Podhradie - Dubná Skala, which has a capital value of more than 2 billion euros. Financial close is anticipated for the fall of 2010, while commercial close was achieved in February 2010.

The Ministry of Telecommunications and Transport has also declared that it will investigate PPP as a method of acquiring components of the Bratislava ring road in the long run. If this

project moves forward, it will also have a large capital value and probably draw interest from foreign buyers.

In Slovakia, the following projects are presently being considered or are the focus of feasibility studies:

- Koice's creative hub
- Bratislava's big hospital construction project.

Slovakia's ongoing road PPP projects have attracted substantial political support at the highest levels. Despite the size of the projects and the state of the market, the private sector has continued to support them thanks to this support and the government's pragmatic approach, particularly that of the Minister of Telecommunications and Transport. If PPP is implemented in other sectors, it should be anticipated that top-level officials and lawmakers from the appropriate departments will support and be actively involved.

Although the Ministries of Finance and Telecommunications and Transport each have distinct PPP sections, Slovakia presently lacks a government PPP authority.

A PPP Forum for the business sector was also established in Slovakia to promote PPP and spread knowledge about it. Slovakia was ranked 18th out of 43 nations in the Europe area and 35th overall in the 2010 Economic Freedom Index, which was issued by the Heritage Foundation and the Wall Street Journal. Overall, it performs better than the global average, and its ratings for corruption-free environments and investment freedom are also above average. Slovakia is the top-ranked nation in the CEE area according to this ranking, where it currently stands.

Overview of legal system

Slovakia is a country that practices civil law and has a civil code. Slovakia's legal framework has been comparatively steady since it underwent significant legislative development in 2004 in anticipation of joining the EU. Laws are changed in response to changes in EU legislation or after consultation with and development by the appropriate Ministries.

Specific PPP/Concession law

There is no formal PPP or concession law in Slovakia. There are certain restrictions for concessions under the Procurement Act (see below), although they mostly have to do with designating a project as a concession rather than limiting other forms of procurement.

The Procurement Act's particular requirements are as follows:

- if the concessionaire previously has or might have revenue from the exploitation, the concession term begins on the first day after the issuance of the opening permit, the occupation permission, or similar event specified in the concession agreement.
- The concessionaire must adhere to certain requirements of the public procurement statute when acquiring important building works if they are to be bid by the concessionaire and not completed by an affiliate of the concessionaire or member of the consortium. This entails disseminating a notice and using open tendering procedures.

The numerous conditions of a concession must be satisfied by the contracts if the project is listed as one in the initial notice of procurement. The aforementioned road projects are being acquired as concessions using a process known as a concession conversation that, in general, resembles the competitive dialogue procurement method.

PPP initiatives have been carried out in Slovakia despite the lack of a PPP or concession law. In general, legislation has not prevented the establishment of PPP contracts based on international risk transfer standards. The Slovak government has handled these concerns in ongoing projects, so they shouldn't prevent the success of these projects. A small number of issues are raised by legislative rules regarding VAT and transfer of the project agreement or concession agreement. In addition, the Ministry of Finance is already putting into practice the findings of a review of current law in an effort to remove the last remaining barriers to PPP projects.

Procurement laws

Public procurement in Slovakia is governed by the Procurement Act of 2006 (the "Procurement Act"). The Procurement Act establishes the four procurement techniques outlined in EU law and transposes the EU procurement guidelines into Slovak law.

- restricted procedure
- negotiated procedure
- competitive discussion
- open procedure.

The so-called concession discussion mechanism, which can be created by public authorities while adhering to the Procurement Act's core principles, is also permitted by the Procurement Act as it has been interpreted by the Slovak procurement office. The Procurement Act's legal elements, which closely resemble the EU's standards for competitive dialogue, will be recognizable to anyone working in procurement throughout Europe. However, it is important to keep in mind that the Procurement Act's interpretation process, as well as general EU procurement regulations, can be rigorous, and meeting qualification requirements may necessitate extensive administrative and legal procedures. Attention to detail in complying with standards is necessary at all levels of procurement, and technical failures to meet criteria, no matter how little, frequently result in exclusion from proceedings.

The Slovak procurement office monitors public procurement operations, and the procurement office also handles objections to and appeals of assessment outcomes.

The limited approach was used to acquire the electronic toll project. However, a concession dialogue approach, which typically resembles the competitive dialogue procedure, is used to procure all of the road PPP projects. Future PPP projects are anticipated to be obtained using the same process or the competitive dialogue process.

As previously mentioned, the Procurement Act has several particular requirements pertaining to what constitutes a concession.

There is no conflict or obligation to combine the two processes because the concession regulations only add a few minor considerations to the basic procedures outlined in the Procurement Act.

Since a new procurement procedure is necessary to change the counterparty to a project agreement or concession agreement, the Procurement Act essentially forbids the transfer of such agreements. This limits the lenders' ability to include step-in or transfer mechanisms in the security package. The Slovak government has acknowledged the limits and limitations that these Procurement Act rules may have on the financing of PPP projects and has attempted to resolve these difficulties in the existing PPP projects through direct agreements with lenders. Below is a more detailed explanation of the strategy used in respect to security problems.

Unsuccessful or de-selected bidders commonly appeal decisions made at all levels of the public procurement process, which is one characteristic of public procurement in Slovakia.

All of the road projects have been impacted by challenges to the procurement office's decisions to reject bids, and the electronic toll PPP project has been delayed as a result of several challenges and appeals to the Slovak procurement office. It is a characteristic of participation in public procurement procedures in the nation that there is a culture of challenges, not only in the PPP market.

Local funding market

Although, like in many jurisdictions at the moment, there are liquidity limits restricting the availability of finance for major transactions, current market input in regard to the road PPP projects shows that there is still desire to finance PPP projects in Slovakia. Multilateral organizations like the EIB and EBRD should continue to play a role in financings in this area. All three of the aforementioned road projects were supposed to reach financial closure within a year, according to the Ministry of Telecommunications and Transport's initial plans. There were hints that collecting more than 113 EUR 5 billion in debt to sustain PPPs in a single year was ambitious, even before the effects of the global crisis. Moving forward, it could be

necessary to create a clear market strategy to guarantee a steady flow of deals without creating rivalry amongst projects in the nation or area. The R1 project, which was the first of the road upgrades, was completed in August 2009. The two remaining projects are anticipated to finish in 2010.

Security issues

According to Slovakian law, lenders can often use security to implement a limited recourse project finance structure. Subcontracts and cash flows may be pledged as security by lenders. Additionally, it is possible to give security over contractor stock shares by both pledges and transfers by means of security. Although the above-discussed limited recourse project finance structure is permitted by the security structures available to lenders, the Procurement Act's provisions do not explicitly permit the transfer of the project agreement or concession agreement to lenders, a nominee, or a replacement contractor. The standard direct agreement safeguards of step-in and replacement of the project agreement are therefore not accessible. As part of the previously indicated legislative push, this issue in the Procurement Act could be remedied. However, this problem has been handled in the road projects by offering substitutes in the form of direct agreements to be made with lenders. The direct agreement contemplates that lenders will be able to implement a remedial plan and exercise controls over the contractor, including the replacement of management or subcontractors and the application of a standstill period while a remedial plan is in operation, rather than being given the opportunity to step-in and assume joint and several liability with the contractor.

Additionally, the direct agreement incorporates clauses that let lenders to acquire and transfer ownership of the contractor in situations where the project agreement would typically be assigned or transferred.

These methods undoubtedly have drawbacks, such as the requirement to justify a non-standard strategy to lenders.

However, it seems that financiers and sponsors of the present road projects have approved them.

Although Slovakia presently lacks a dedicated PPP statute, there aren't many substantial barriers to the execution of successful PPP projects in the legal system. Further law changes to solve problems that have developed in connection with the present projects might follow from the Ministry of Finance's examination of the PPP legal framework. The Slovak government has already given its approval to this assessment, and the suggested revisions will become legislation in 2010 and 2011.

The main problems that have so far shown up in PPP projects in Slovakia are:

- A project agreement or concession agreement cannot be transferred to a third party without a fresh procurement because of clauses in the Procurement Act that do not clearly permit this and so effectively forbid it. This has an effect on the lenders' ability to move projects or intervene in the event of a default. This problem has been resolved in the recent PPP projects by clauses in the direct agreement.
- Even though payment for the construction is being delayed, under Slovak VAT law, VAT becomes due on the value of a structure or asset upon transfer to the public body (e.g. through future availability payments). This might have the result that the contractor or concessionaire using would have to use loan facilities to pay the tax authorities' VAT. The public authority will pay this VAT duty to the contractor or concessionaire as soon as possible before payment becomes due to the tax authorities, which addresses the concern that this arrangement does not offer value for money.

4.5 PPPs in Italy

Although the current global economic crisis has had an impact on the country and produced a GDP decline of roughly 5% for 2009 (compared to a decline of about 1% in 2008), Italy's economy is still comparatively stable. The drop in international demand has had an impact on

industrial production and investments. Additionally, current public spending climbed by an additional 3% in 2009 after reaching its greatest level since World War 2.

In order to comply with the Maastricht Treaty's criteria, the Italian government has authorized a financial plan that aims to reduce the debt/GDP ratio to 3% over the next three years. The strategy should reduce costs associated with providing public services and stop tax evasion. Nevertheless, real economy qualitative measures are gradually beginning to reflect a weakening of the recessionary trend.

Fiscal federalism is one of the urgent stabilizing measures that the administration implemented for 2009–2010 in order to help with spending reduction (by lowering State expenditures associated with reallocating public economic resources, which will be maintained in the local region from where they originate). The consequences of the unstable economy, which presently accounts for 15% of total economic output, will also be mitigated by simplifying the law and improving governmental intervention.

Additionally, the building and installation of high-speed rail systems, whose expenditures are currently adversely hurting the government's balance sheet in compared to other European nations, are given top priority. In terms of infrastructure policy, the Italian government unveiled a plan for the development and building of extensive infrastructure costing more than EUR 16 billion towards the end of 2008. To improve the initiatives previously specified in 2007, some of this investment will consist of fresh government funding, while other projects will be privately sponsored (mainly dedicated to motorways). The government has also set aside an additional EUR 11 billion for infrastructure improvement in 2010, including initiatives like the Milan Expo (\$1.5 billion) and the Salerno-Reggio Calabria motorway (\$1 billion).

The following industries have seen PPP contracts granted as part of the 2008 infrastructure program:

- Energy and telecoms saw 104 projects granted for a total of 659 million euros;
- sport venues saw 50 projects awarded for a total of 146 million euros;

- parking lots saw 44 projects awarded for a total of 149 million euros;
- schools saw 36 projects awarded for a total of 131 million euros.

Although a limited number of high value projects were given in some sectors, such as transportation and roads, whereby two projects were granted for a total consideration of EUR 2.2 million, the pattern indicates that investors are more interested in projects worth less than EUR 1 million.

In 2009, many PPP contracts were granted, particularly in industries like:

- Motorways: Improvements to the "A4" Novara-Milano freeway and the "Asse Pedemontano" road (Piemonte Lombardia and Veneto Regions);
- Transportation: a significant and expensive bridge system connecting the regions of Calabria and Sicily;
- Rail: Brescia and Monza are getting new subterranean railways, and Naples is improving its existing system;
- Seaport Hubs (with roughly 100 million euros in private funding)

This organization is in charge of assisting local governments in determining which of their infrastructure project requirements are appropriate for private capital financing, offering excellent value for money. Additionally, the UTFP wants to help local authorities evaluate project ideas submitted by promoters, file the necessary paperwork, and announce the opening of tenders for the project. Italy was ranked 74th overall and 35th in the European zone in the 2010 Economic Freedom Index, which was issued by the Heritage Foundation and the Wall Street Journal. This score increased from 2009, placing Italy just above the global average.

Overview of legal system

Italy is a country with a civil law system that is governed by several laws and rules. Italy's legislative system is mostly stable, and amendments are often made to incorporate changes to EU law or as a result of discussion and development by the relevant ministries and other governmental authorities.

On June 18, 2009, the civil procedure law and the civil code underwent the most recent modification in Italy in order to streamline the judicial process.

Specific PPP/Concession law

Plans for public works projects costing more than EUR 100,000 are organized through a three-year schedule, with yearly updates determined by the awarding authority and written and published in accordance with the relevant town planning legislation and the existing legal framework. Priority projects must be covered by such programs.

PPP initiatives may be implemented using a variety of techniques.

Project finance

One-stage procedure: The awarding authorities may grant a concession on the basis of a call for competition based on a feasibility study issued by the awarding authority in order to realize the public works or the works of public interest that are listed by the three-year program and are suitable for being privately financed. Any economic operator (known as a Promotore) is permitted to propose a project that has been developed using such a feasibility study. The selecting authority will choose the chosen project and may request that the appropriate Promotore make any changes to it. If the favored Promotore rejects the recommended changes, the awarding authority may ask for the identical changes to be made to the Promotore's proposal that placed second in the selection process.

Two-stage procedure: The selection process will not determine whether the selected Promotore receives the concession, but rather whether it will have the opportunity to be chosen over the best tenderer should it modify its offer to one that is deemed to be more advantageous. The awarding authorities may also publish a call for competition. The Promotore is given this privilege for a 45-day period. The best tenderer will get the Promotore to cover the costs incurred for its participation in the competition if the chosen Promotore exercises its pre-emption right after previously amending its offer in line with any incidental superior offer. The same compensation is given to the Promoter at the tenderer's expense if it does not use its pre-emption right as stated above.

In any instance, the reimbursement amount cannot be greater than 2.5% of the investment's value as stated in the feasibility study that served as the foundation for the call for competition.

Concessions

A "public works concession" is an agreement of the same kind as a public projects contract, with the exception that the economic operators are only required to pay for the privilege of using the infrastructure for their own economic gain.

The concession, which can last up to 30 years, gives the concessionaire the right to run the developed infrastructure and collect operating revenue. A public call for competition in which competitors must fulfill certain technical and financial criteria is used to award the concession. According to the "most economically beneficial offer" criteria, the tender is chosen.

Public procurement - Italy's Code, which applied Eu Legislation 2004/17 and 2004/18, governs public procurements.

The following technique can be used to issue concessions:

a) open procedure: where each bidder makes their offer in accordance with the guidelines outlined in the invitation to bid;

b) restricted procedure: In this process, each applicant must submit an expression of curiosity in accordance with the guidelines outlined in the call for competition. Following this stage, the economic operator who meets the requirements submits a bid in accordance with the guidelines outlined in the invitation to tender sent by the awarding authority.

The Code also governs the selection processes for goods, services, and public works projects. In accordance with these rules, the awarding Authority searches for business entities to provide supplies, services, and works in exchange for payment in advance. This is the fundamental distinction between these processes and PPPs, where the favored tenderer gets compensated through the use of the constructed infrastructure.

The Code allows for a variety of techniques to be utilized to pick the best tender for public contracts based on the lowest price or the most advantageous tender from an economic standpoint.

These processes, in addition to those described above for concessions:

a) negotiated procedure, in which the awarding Authorities and a limited number of applicants discuss the conditions of the contract;

b) competitive dialogue: This method is used for complicated public procurements (i.e., when the granting Authority is unable to precisely figure out the specific specifications for the planned public works, services, or supplies), and it involves several stages. By using the awarding criteria outlined in the call for competition, this method assists in reducing the number of solutions that must be discussed during the discussion stage.

Local funding market

Since 1999, Italy has been a member of the Eurozone. In 2002, Italy formally adopted the Euro, with a fixed exchange rate of 1 Euro for 1936.27 Italian Lira. Only business dealings with nations outside the Euro zone will be affected by any changes in the Euro's exchange rate.

Italy's inflation rate does not experience major swings.

PPP projects are financed privately, mostly through the private partner's own assets and debt (such as bank loans and bonds). Private equity funds and European infrastructure funds are other funding sources. The financing of very expensive equipment is facing a significant decline due to the present global economic slowdown. However, as public works, services, and supplies provided by commercial enterprises are reimbursed directly by public authorities, public procurements are only slightly declining. Therefore, the function of financial parties is less important for such initiatives.

Security issues

The following guarantees must be included in each offer made for a competition in accordance with Articles 113 and 75 of the Code:

- a down payment equal to 2% of the contract's value;
- 2.5% of the contract's value in the form of a bond, deposit, or first demand guarantee provided by a bank or an insurance provider.

However, these assurances may be decreased by 50% if the ultimately chosen tenderer is an organization that has been certified in accordance with European ISO 9000 guidelines.

As soon as the chosen tenderer receives the contract, it is required to produce a first demand guarantee from a bank or insurance firm in the amount of 10% of the contract value, which will be gradually lowered to 75% of the baseline secured amount as the work progresses.

Such a guarantee is given to ensure that the chosen tenderer will carry out the contract, and the remaining 25% is released once the test certificate or the certificate for the correct completion of the job has been granted. The guarantee's dollar value might need to be adjusted.

A 10% deposit of the yearly running expenses associated with the relevant public work must also be provided by the chosen tenderer in addition to the aforementioned guarantee in order to assure correct payment of any necessary penalties in the event of contract breach.

Italian banks are often willing to finance on a full-recourse or limited-recourse basis, depending on the security package typically demanded by the lenders.

The security package often includes personal guarantees from the shareholders as well as securities over assets (mortgages on building leasing rights, buildings, lands, pledges over shares of the contractor), as well as securities over revenue from the exploitation of the infrastructure. The law that governs PPP proceedings also gives lenders the authority to intervene in any contract that the contractor enters into, including the concession contract.

Reaction of the government to the financial crisis

A number of actions have been taken by the Italian government in response to the financial crisis, most notably Resolution No. 32009 of March 6, 2009, issued by the CIPE, which calls for additional public funding to be allocated for infrastructure projects deemed to be strategic assets for the country's economic and social advancement.

This rise has led to an additional investment of EUR 5 billion in strategic and transportation infrastructures, environmental recovery, archaeological and museum infrastructure, and school safety, with 85% of the commitment going to southern areas and 15% going to northern regions. As these measures have not yet been put into action, it is currently impossible to assess their efficacy.

Both public procurement and PPP are governed by the Code of Public Contracts established by Legislative Decree 163 of 2006. Many PPP contracts were granted in 2008 and 2009 under its processes, with a trend indicating significant interest in projects costing less than EUR 1 million.

The following are the biggest concerns with PPP in Italy right now:

- a significant decrease in the purchase of very expensive infrastructure projects as a result of the global economic slump;
- a lack of confidence in the awarding processes due to the frequent appeals of awarding decisions, which can result in the suspension of the pertinent works

4.6 PPPs in Azerbaijan

PPP just began operations in Azerbaijan. The Law on the Implementation of Special Financing for Investment Projects in Connection with Infrastructure and Construction Facilities, sometimes known as "the Law," was approved in 2016. Without mentioning other models, the PPP legislation in Azerbaijan typically offers procedures for the possible financing of the BOT model. However, the PPP legislation also contains Rules "On the Application of the Infrastructure Projects by Investors under the Build-Operate-Transfer Model, Specifications to the Investor, the Terms and Conditions of the Agreements and Determination of the Cost of Goods and Services Produced Under the Investments," approved by the Presidential Decree later in 2016. For the BOT model to be implemented in Azerbaijan, these Rules envision a more detailed regulatory structure and requirements, which include the following:

- 1) requirements for carrying out investment initiatives;
- 2) criteria for investors based on the kind of infrastructure and building projects;
- 3) the conditions of contracts reached with investors;
- 4) guidelines for calculating the costs of products and services generated as a consequence of investments.

Projects involving public-private partnerships have already been carried out in Azerbaijan - In addition to the BOT model and prior to passing the BOT Law, Azerbaijan has carried out a number of projects that are PPPs by definition. One such project, carried out by CNIM Group, relates to the building and operation of a waste-to-energy facility. The design, building, and 20-

year management of an energy recovery plant was given to CNIM by the state-owned business Tamiz Shahar JSC, which is in charge of using the city of Baku's solid municipal trash. A management contract is one type of public-private cooperation. The administration of the Central Clinic during a 10-year period by the Turkish business "AY-MED Medical Yatirim Danishmanlik Ticaret" is an example of this form of PPP. PPP is really often utilized in the healthcare sector around the globe in one of three primary ways: 1) to develop or renovate public healthcare infrastructure, 2) to increase or extend service delivery capacity, or 3) to offer a complete package of infrastructure and service delivery. Azerbaijan's Shahdag Winter-Summer Tourism Complex, a division of the State Tourism Agency, and PGI Management inked a management agreement for the Shahdag Ski Resort as another illustration of PPP in the form of a contract agreement.

The BOT agreement's duration is similarly capped at 49 years under the law, and it must be signed by both the investor and the public sector (Ministry of Economy of the Republic of Azerbaijan is the authorized body to execute BOT agreements, supervise PPP projects etc.) The administration of building and infrastructure facilities will be given to the Ministry of Economy when the specified time period has passed, and they will be free of all debts and liabilities of any type and adequate for their intended purpose. According to the Law, the facilities may be acquired from the investors before the period expires for state requirements, provided that all of their expenses and anticipated project earnings would be reimbursed. The Rules govern the selection of BOT private partners, which is a distinct procedure under Azerbaijani PPP law. Additionally, the BOT projects are exempt from the "On State Procurement" requirements of the Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

We have outlined the legislation's primary beneficial aspects and its primary shortcomings in order to examine the PPP framework in greater detail.

Main advantages

The following are some of the primary benefits of PPP legislation:

- The public sector may provide the investor additional assurances, such as paying the budgeted amounts that customers were supposed to pay when the BOT facility was in operation.
- The state guarantees the public sector's liabilities;
- Under the BOT agreement, the state guarantees the public sector's debts.
- PPP projects are exempt from the provisions of the Law "On Public Procurement."

Main gaps

Given that PPPs are new to Azerbaijan and that the PPP legislative framework has only recently been adopted, there are some gaps that must be filled before PPPs can become a more widely used and preferred method for investors to participate in large-scale infrastructure and other projects in Azerbaijan. The following are the gaps:

- The BOT model is the only one supported under PPP legislation. Under previous PPP models, this is one of the primary problems that restricts private sector involvement in the project. Greater freedom will be provided by the law.
- There is no clear definition of who is in charge of the project during the building and running phases. Therefore, it is unclear whether the public or private sector will own the project;
- Other organizations outside the Ministry of Economy have defined roles in the contemporary public sector. As a result, this may cause administrative and procedural obstacles. Additionally, various governmental entities who actually order infrastructure facilities to be built using private sector funding under the PPP model have limited control over monitoring during the contract execution term, which may lead to inferior quality projects and services.

Infrastructure Financing Using the Traditional Method - Although there has been a sharp rise in private sector involvement in infrastructure projects throughout the CIS area, the conventional

method of financing infrastructure remains dominant. Historically, state funds have been used by governments to fund infrastructure initiatives. Financing a project exclusively out of government funds has a number of disadvantages:

- Public money may only be accessible for the project's first phases for large infrastructure projects, which sometimes take many years to construct. Therefore, if there is any doubt about the future availability of funding to execute the project, government agencies are wary about devoting time to the planning stage;
- The capital component of the budget for the pertinent government ministry is sometimes given an excessive amount of attention;
- The expenses of the project in relation to the capital returns are not balanced. To make sure that the investment would add value and support national economic expansion, it is critical to balance the project expenses against the capital returns.

Alternatives to "traditional" public procurement, such as PPPs

The private sector can finance public infrastructure projects in a variety of ways. The "conventional" public procurement is at one end of the spectrum, and total privatization is at the other. PPPs are essentially the middle ground between full privatization of government assets and "conventional" public procurement. The main variations are:

- Unlike "conventional" public procurement, requirements in PPPs are defined in terms of "outputs" rather than "inputs";
- The asset must be financed, built, and operated by the private sector;
- Through recurring payments (services payments) or revenue created (user fees) during the course of the contract, the public sector "purchases" the services;
- Risks related to expenses of design, building, operation, and maintenance, as well as demand for the usage and service supplied by the asset, are shifted from the public to the

private sector in a PPP project; any cost overruns in a PPP remain at the risk of the private sector;

- In a PPP, the private sector pays for construction expenses, reducing pressure on government financing for infrastructure projects needing substantial capital investments;
- Comparing the PPP model to traditional procurement, the complete life-cycle approach guarantees that the private sector chooses the most effective and sustainable solution over the long term rather than the cheapest one over the short term.

4.6.1 Legal basis

In addition to the BOT Law, the President of Azerbaijan issued a decree on December 7th, 2016 known as the "BOT Order," which sets forth specifics of the terms of the investment, criteria for private investors, the selection process for investors, etc. According to the BOT Law, the BOT model is a particular type of project financing in which investors recover their investment costs for projects involving infrastructure items by selling goods or services to clients or appropriate governmental entities. The Ministry of Economy of the Republic of Azerbaijan is the appropriate entity in charge of implementing the BOT model in that country and represents the public sector in PPP agreements.

According to the BOT agreement, the BOT model is applicable to the building, restoration, rebuild, repair, operation, and transfer of bridges, tunnels, water warehouses, water cleaning plants - constructions, sewage systems, and other publicly significant infrastructure items. According to the BOT Law and BOT Order (together, "BOT law"), the BOT model's approach for fostering collaboration between the public and private sectors is divided into the following steps:

- Step 1: The sectoral authority submits an application to the competent authority (the Ministry of Economy of the Republic of Azerbaijan) with a proposal that covers the

technical background, a general definition of the needs for infrastructure and services, and an analysis of institutional options for the specific project (the "Project").

- Step 2: The Ministry of Economy completes the criteria for a possible investor and announces the bidding procedure, which is controlled by the BOT Law, following the first evaluation and approval of the Project. The Law of State Procurement's requirements are not applicable.
- Step 3: The potential investor must submit a process and project estimate as part of the bidding process.
- Step 4: Following the conclusion of the bidding procedure and the selection of the investor based on the supplied documents, the chosen Investor should create a legal organization (the "Project Company") that is only allowed to oversee the project. Following that, the Ministry of Economy and the chosen investor ("Investor") come to a BOT Agreement on the Project's implementation.
- Step 5: BOT contracts may last up to 49 years. The government should receive the facilities back after the contract time is finished (they were constructed and run by the Investor / Project Company).

4.6.2 Institutional factors and controlling financial risks

According to the experience of various countries, the institutional ability is a crucial component in organizing, managing, and putting a PPP process into practice. The Government of Azerbaijan currently lacks a central PPP unit that would be in charge of carrying out risk estimate, monitoring, managing, and reporting associated operations for a PPP project. The creation and execution of PPP projects is the responsibility of the relevant governmental authorities, which include the Ministry of Economy and the Small and Medium-Sized Business Development Agency ("SMBDA"). When it comes to controlling the fiscal risks associated with sovereign guarantees, the Ministry of Finance (MoF) is important.

The BOT Law sets the yearly amount of sovereign guarantee for work done under the BOT model at 10% of the cost of the project as one approach to limit the fiscal risks. Additionally, based on the government commitment included in the budget for the relevant year, the Ministries of Finance and Economy estimate yearly guarantee responsibilities for projects performed using the BOT model. The Ministry of Economy works with the Ministry of Finance to undertake a techno-economic assessment before choosing the investor to carry out an infrastructure project. The Ministry of Economy works with the Ministry of Finance to produce a draft BOT Contract for the investment project after the decision to undertake a project using the BOT model has been made. They also create implementation benchmarks against which the project's performance is measured. In addition to the aforementioned precautions, other safety procedures are also in place to handle unanticipated circumstances. The Ministry of Economy is permitted to use the safeguard fund to manage fiscal risks, such as when the competent authority has given the investor a tariff or revenue guarantee, such guarantee to buy services or goods or to pay the service fees on behalf of the populace. The government has created a "safeguard fund" within the state budget.

Despite the aforementioned, it is equally crucial to establish a strong, well-rounded supervision mechanism for controlling fiscal risks associated with PPPs. A robust, efficient financial supervision structure must be in place to handle the fiscal risks associated with PPP projects, according to the global experience of expensive PPP failures.

Risk allocation

According to the BOT Law, the Investor—which may be either a natural person or a legal entity—participates in the bidding process, invests money in the project, and is a party to the BOT Contract. What then is the Project Company's function? The BOT Act makes it clear that the major goal of creating a Project Company is to give the Ministry of Economy the ability to manage and oversee the Project on behalf of the Government. As a result, there remain unanswered questions, such as who will be in charge of carrying out the Project and how the parties would divide the risks and obligations. It is more effective to manage a project

collaboratively if it has several substantial hazards, i.e., by accepting and spreading the risks with the design, the constructor, and/or the operator/maintainer, instead of designating them to a specific party.

4.6.3 Property and Tax issues

Property issues

Instead of building the facilities from scratch, the Project may in some situations call for the transfer of some State-owned properties or land to a private investor for repair work. The ownership concerns are not covered by the BOT Legislation. The Government Property Issues Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan is the entity that represents the State with regard to the property that is owned by public bodies and state-owned legal entities, in accordance with Azerbaijani law, specifically the Action of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan on acceptance of the Government Program on Continuing to improve Management of State Property in the Republic of Azerbaijan.

This leads us to the reasonable conclusion that the Ministry of Economy, which is the competent body for carrying out BOT projects, is not qualified nor permitted to transfer any government property (facilities) to a private investor in accordance with the BOT Contract.

Regarding the land, the situation is the same. The private investor may desire to guarantee his rights to certain assets and land while participating in an infrastructure project. The State shall continue to be the land's owner throughout the term of the BOT Agreement, and the private investor should continue to be the owner of the facilities while taking on the responsibilities and rights of a usufructuary with relation to the land the facilities are built on.

Proposed regulations - A clear title to the land as well as other state-owned property as well as the range of rights that the Investor acquires over the BOT Agreement's term are what the public sector aims to give. Who is deemed to be the owner of the facilities during the operation

period—the Investor, the State, or the Project Company? If the State, whose state authorities execute the rights of ownership on behalf of the State for BOT purposes?—should be made explicit in the law. It would be necessary to develop a streamlined process for requesting approval from the State Property Issues Committee or to grant the Ministry of Economy or other established PPP body the ability to act on behalf of the State with regard to state-owned property for BOT Agreement purposes.

Tax issues

The Tax Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan is not superseded by the BOT Statute, hence the main provisions of the statutory tax regime created by the Tax Code should apply to the PPP law.

Balance sheet treatment - The right to allocate the resources to its balance and determine the depreciation expenses with regard to the facilities is another open topic in addition to the ownership problem. According to the rationale of the IFRS norm, assets should be shown on the balance of the business that will benefit from the asset's future economic advantages. Within the financial leasing agreement, it might either be the owner or the lessee. The Tax Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan and IFRS define financial leasing, and facilities managed under the BOT model would probably come under this category, giving the authority to depreciate the assets.

However, the current "financial leasing" rules of the Tax Code may be interpreted to prevent a tax payer from deducting expenses from their taxes. What if the Project Company really uses the assets and facilities in its entrepreneurial operations, yet the Investor is the party to the BOT Agreement and the organization investing in the building or repair of any state-owned facility. Which entity's balance should in this case represent the given property?

The Project Company's financial sheet should contain the right response. It is necessary to have a legal foundation, such as a piece of law or a contract, in order to assign the asset (institutions) to the Project Company's balance sheet. The Investor may transfer the capacity to a Project

Company for management and operation based on a contract because there is no legal basis for doing so. As a result, this transfer will be considered taxable alienation and be liable to VAT and profit tax.

Transfer of assets

Several times during the course of the BOT Project's existence, assets (other than the repaired facility) will be transferred from the Government to the Investor, from of the Investor to a Project Company, and vice versa. For the duration of the BOT Project's full lifespan, treating such a transfer as a taxable event will result in increased tax and compliance burdens for all BOT Project participants in each of the following transactions:

1. The State transfers the facilities to the Investor
2. The project company receives the resources from the investor.
3. Giving the Investor their money back for the amenities
4. Giving the State its facilities back

Proposed regulations.

Any property transfer between BOT Project participants should not be regarded as just a taxable sale under profit tax or VAT purposes and may instead be seen as a tax-neutral transaction.

Dividend payments.

BOT law stipulates that the Project Company must be established. The investor that provided the money for the project wanted a return on its investment. If a project company is established, any earnings made during operations may only be transferred to the investor in the form of dividends subject to source-based withholding tax.

Proposed regulations.

The creation of a Project Company is a legally required necessity, thus in our opinion, the Investor shouldn't be subject to any additional taxes on their investment's return. Exempting dividend payout from the a Project Company to the Investor from of the Withholding Tax is Advisable in Order to Attract Private Investor Interest to a Infrastructure Investment

4.6.4 Future of PPP in Azerbaijan

This section describes the attitudes of the business sector in Azerbaijan about involvement in PPP projects based on the findings of in-depth interviews. Additionally, it explores the prospects for private sector participation in construction projects in Azerbaijan and offers a concise list of queries that must be addressed by the government before a decision about such participation can be made. It should be noted, however, that thorough risk assessments, feasibility, and sustainability development studies are required for each of the possibilities listed below; therefore, this document is not intended to serve as a substitute for such studies.

A) Private sector participation options in PPP

In Azerbaijan, there are several alternatives for private sector participation in PPP projects, depending on who controls the assets, who is in charge of maintenance and operations who decides whether to invest, and who assumes operational risks.

OPTION	ASSET OWNERSHIP	MAINTENANCE	INVESTMENT DECISION	OPERATIONAL RISKS
Management & lease contracts	Public	Private	Public	Public/private (public under management; private under lease contract)
Concessions	Public	Private	Private	Private
Greenfield projects	Public/private (ownership may return to public sector or remain with private sector)	Private	Private	Private (revenue guarantees may or may not be provided)
Divesture	Public/private (either 100% or part of equity stakes are bought by private sector)	Private	Private	Private

Table 1. Private sector participation options in PPP

Azerbaijan has experience putting three of the four abovementioned ideas into practice:

- 1) Energy sector concession agreements, when a private corporation acquires a state-owned facility, renovates it, and then uses and maintains it on its own risk for the duration of the agreement (25years).
- 2) In the telecommunications industry, greenfield contracts are used, in which private sponsors construct a new facility before owning and operating it. Private sponsors assume all risks. In two instances (Azercell and Bakcell), the contract types provide for baseline traffic revenue guarantees or long-term take-or-pay agreements for bulk supply facilities to give government revenue guarantees. After the concession time is through, the facility will be returned to the public sector (15-20 years). However, the government does not guarantee any revenue in the remaining two cases (Narmobile and CATEL)

- 3) Management and lease contract in water sector (the case of joint venture in Imishli studied above), where private entity took over the management of a state-owned enterprise for a fixed period (10 years) while ownership and investment decisions remained with the state.

4.7 Statistics and analysis of the European public-private partnership market in 2021

Overview - The overall amount of PPP agreements in the European market that reached financial closure in 2021 was €8.0 billion, a 13% decline from €9.2 billion in 2020.

Figure 3. 2012-2021 years view of the European PPP market by value and number of projects (World Bank)

- As opposed to 43 in 2020, there were 40 PPP transactions that reached financial closure.
- From €215 million in 2020, the average transaction size dropped to €201 million in 2019.

- In 2021, three significant transactions were completed as opposed to seven in 2020. They were worth a total of €3.8 billion, or 47% (as opposed to 60% in 2020) of the market value. The significant deals that were completed financially in 2021 were:
 - 1) Pedemontana Lombarda Motorway (Italy) €2.1 billion;
 - 2) Aydin-Denizli-Burdur Motorway (Turkey) €1.1 billion;
 - 3) D4 Expressway (Haje-Mirotice) (Czech Republic) — €530 million

- Demand-based PPP accounted for 68% of closed agreements in 2021 (up from 61% in 2020), a notable rise from 2012 when just 8% of transactions reached financial close.

- The number of concluded PPP transactions decreased somewhat in 2021 (from 43 to 40 projects), which shows that COVID-19's effects on project planning and procurement were less severe than anticipated. However, the pandemic's impacts are still being felt and will probably be noticeable in the years to come.

4.7.1 Country Breakdown

Italy had the highest PPP market value in Europe, at €2.2 billion (\$473 million in 2020), as seen in Figure 4. The Pedemontana Lombarda Motorway Concession's presence is what accounts for the projects in Italy in 2021 having a very high value. With an estimated €4.1 billion in total investment expenses, the contract was granted in 2008. The Varese and Como ring roads are part of Sections A and B1, which were finished and put into service in 2015. The financial closure for sections B2 and C was reached in 2021, and building is expected to start in the second part of 2022 and be finished in late 2025. Section D's building work is anticipated to begin in 2025.

With 17 finalized transactions, France led all other PPP markets in terms of the quantity of projects.

Figure 4. Country breakdown in 2021 for PPP projects based on value and number (World Bank)

- France ranked second in terms of value for public-private partnerships, with a sum of €1.4 billion (€2.4 billion euro in 2020).
- Five nations finalized at least two contracts (and five more in 2020), and 13 countries completed at least one PPP contract (compared to 11 in 2020).

4.7.2 Sector Breakdown

- According to Figure 5, with €6.0 billion in transactions (up from €5.8 billion in 2020), the transport industry continued to be the largest in terms of value. With 16 transportation projects nearing financial closure in 2021 as opposed to 12 in 2020, the number of projects grew.
- Nine environmental projects with a combined value of €866 m (€658 m in 2020) were completed. With four district heating projects, it was the second-most active industry in terms of value and projects.

- The telecoms industry closed three projects with a combined value of €427 m (€1.1 b in 2020) as opposed to four in 2020. All three purchases included broadband in France.
- The number of projects in the education sector that achieved financial close fell from 11 to 5, and the overall value fell to €391 m (€866 m in 2020).
- The recreation and culture industry saw four transactions with a combined value of €126 m (€410 m in 2020) as opposed to six in 2020. Three of them were water parks (France, Germany and Poland).

Figure 5. Sector breakdown in 2021 based on the value and quantity of PPP projects (World Bank)

4.7.3 Project Pipeline

The three states with the most projects in the works, according to Figure 6, are France (53 projects), Belgium (25 projects), and Italy (19 projects).

Although the UK's central government stopped utilizing PFI and PF2 for new projects, the public-private partnership model is still utilized in the nation's student housing, care facilities, and energy-from-waste industries.

Figure 6. By country, the number of PPP pipeline projects (World Bank)

- The pipeline continues to be dominated by projects in the transportation industry, which is followed by projects in the environment and education (Figure 7).
- The environment and transportation sectors account for more over two-thirds of the French pipeline of projects. Six of the 18 transportation projects are for urban transportation, three are for railroads, and 14 of the 20 environmental projects involve district heating.
- Austria has submitted a bid to construct the fiber network in the Liezen neighborhood. This project is a component of the government's strategic strategy to provide fiber connectivity across the nation and encompasses the 50-year design, construction, financing, operation, and maintenance of the regional fiber network.

Figure 7. Number of projects by sector in the pipeline (World Bank)

Annex 1

Large PPP projects (€500 million or more) as a proportion of overall activity in 2021

World Bank

Annex 2

World Bank

Annex 3

World Bank

Data and methodology

This research will be carried out using secondary data from several sources. The secondary data gathered from official statistical documents, published books, journals, research papers, magazines, daily newspapers, and the internet. Any secondary data that is examined to response a research question can be included in the analysis of secondary data. In the context and conduct of a research project, secondary data can be used for different ways. Finding the research problem, formulating a plan to solve the problem, determining the responses to specific research questions, identifying potential issues, gathering the necessary background data, and enhancing the study's credibility are all possible benefits of this research.

This research used a quantitative method. The data collected from already-existing data sources. It involves gathering data, which frequently yields numerically structured information. When a researcher wants to answer the "what" or "how many" questions in a research question, they use quantitative data. It consists of information that can be compared numerically or counted. Data used in the study was gathered from the World Bank and UNCTAD (United Nations Conference on Trade and Development).

Conclusions and recommendations

As the examples above show, PPPs may assist governments in infrastructure and other significant projects should be carried out with shared responsibility and at the lowest possible cost. Given the assurances from the public sector and the shared obligations between the parties, this is also advantageous for the private sector.

The introduction of the BOT model in Azerbaijan is a step toward including the private sector in major infrastructure projects as a shareholder rather than just as a contractor. As long as there are assurances in place, this will also assist reduce government spending on projects which the private sector can handle. Moreover, in order to draw in investors, we are going to strengthen the PPP legal framework, fill up any gaps that exist, develop procedures for PPP models other than BOT, and regularly update the private sector—whether local or global—on our progress in strengthening the PPP system.

It is necessary to list a few issues that discourage new PPP projects in Azerbaijan:

- The government presently has a major role in regulating service quality and establishing rates in Azerbaijan.
- The national budget has access to large financial resources because of the oil resources. Therefore, the government may not always view PPP as an appealing choice. PPP is often sought on the government's end and is regarded as a measure to minimize ongoing public subsidies.
- Government control over tariffs reduces the private sector's ability to set prices. Additionally, when tariffs are less expensive than the going rate for a given service, financial viability depends on government assistance.

- Although the overall legal climate is thought to be favorable for PPP, there are holes in the legislation governing concessions and a subpar court system. Transaction costs rise as a result of high corruption risk and legislative anomalies.
- The financial viability of projects that would not be capable of covering costs from the customer fee collection face substantial risks due to the poor ability of customers to pay for the services. The situation is made worse by high restoration costs and unequal risk allocation.

All of these elements play a role in the private sector's choice to participate in PPP projects around the nation. Despite these obstacles, however, collaborative private-public initiatives and more policy talks may assist resolve these problems and support reaping the benefits of PPP. The government should formalize PPP by incorporating this concept into current laws and rules and by outlining a potential PPP model for Azerbaijan. A suitable current legislation will also provide the private sector certainty that the government is committed to the problem and that possible contracts would be upheld. This will need for amendments to already existing legislation, the creation of new legislation specifically addressing PPP as a policy alternative, or maybe both.

Given the international experience of development fueled by mineral resource exploitation and wasteful expenditure by central governments, current re-centralization tendencies should be carefully examined.

Summary

The expression of a lack of financial resources, which is used as an excuse for the state's failure to properly fulfill its constitutionally mandated public service obligations in social and economic fields, is becoming increasingly ineffective. In other words, at the point of delivery of public services governed by the Constitution and shaped by laws, public administrations now have private sector support. A new contract type has been added to the long-standing method of making public services available to private individuals. This type of contract is a "public private cooperation" method, which has its own characteristics and whose legal boundaries must be drawn with a successful law.

When the public-private cooperation model is examined, concrete criticisms are found, such as public resources being wasted, care and quality in the provision of public services deteriorating, trust and loyalty to the state deteriorating, and mistakes being made in the public service planning process. It has even been suggested that the regulation in question is a deception and expression game designed to eliminate the negative aspects of privatization's concept and content. In addition to the necessity of enacting a general and detailed law to refute these criticisms, the relevant ministries should also issue sample contract texts. These contracts, for example, should be made by experts in their fields, and all possible outcomes should be considered. As a result, in the event of a potential conflict, both the public and private sectors will have the opportunity to understand their full duties and responsibilities ahead of schedule and act accordingly.

The goal of public-private partnership projects is to overcome the challenges of financing the establishment of public facilities and structures while also reducing the risks associated with the project. Although it is stated that the aforementioned model has no absolute advantage over the traditional public service production model in terms of achieving the desired results, and even fails because it introduces new risks in many areas, these drawbacks can be overcome with the right approach. Considering that the private sector will cover all costs during the establishment phase of these facilities, and in planning the reduction of said costs through long contracts, it is

ensured that the state acts with caution. If the anticipated period is reduced to 49 years at most, the government's reliance on the private sector will become excessive. If so many different and large contracts are made over such a long period of time, and the total rental costs are considered, it will be impossible for the state to establish and operate a public service on its own, and the contracting tradition will become a vicious circle. In light of this possibility, and despite the fact that the service in question can be set up for free at first, it will be concluded that this thesis will be more costlier in the long run.

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